

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

Partnerships & Applications Workshop June 26-27, 2025

Workshop Report

Prepared by: Andy Clifford, Valerie Sahakian, and Jill Elizabeth

**Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center
Partnerships & Applications Workshop
June 26-27, 2025**

Workshop Report

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
Introduction	3
Workshop Overview	3
Workshop Purpose, Goals and Design	3
Participation and Representation	5
Discussion Summaries	7
A. Cascadia Connections Exercise	7
B. Science To Practice Reflection	7
C. Addressing Science Communication Challenges	10
D. Cascadia Scenario Needs	12
E. Building a Cascadia Data Dashboard	13
F. Addressing Skills Gaps, Training Needs & Geosciences Education Opportunities	15
Next Steps.....	17
2025-26 Priorities	18
Acknowledgements	18
Appendices	19
Appendix I – Workshop Agenda	19
Appendix 2 – Poster And Digital Media Presentations	23
Posters.....	23
Digital Media	24
Appendix 3 – Reflection Activity Responses	25
Appendix 4 – Evaluation Responses.....	27
Appendix 5 – Cascadia Connections Map	31

Executive Summary

The 2025 Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center (CRESCENT) Partnerships & Applications (P&A) Workshop, held June 26–27 at the University of Oregon’s NE Portland campus, convened participants from research, federal, tribal, state and local government, emergency management, education, and community organizations across the Cascadia region. Building on insights from the 2024 inaugural workshop, the 2025 event deepened focus on four emergent themes: science communication, emergency preparedness and response planning, data access, and resource limitations. Through interactive exercises, case studies, roundtables, and presentations, participants identified critical needs for improved interorganizational coordination, accessible data and tools, scenario-based planning, and expanded education and training pathways to strengthen the earthquake resilience ecosystem.

Key outcomes included a vision for developing a Cascadia Connections Map as an interactive resource to visualize and strengthen networks across the resilience community and consensus to prioritize scenario development as next year’s P&A Workshop theme. Participants also called for expanded partnerships to address geoscience skills gaps and workforce development needs. The report concludes with near-term CRESCENT actions and identifies priorities for the upcoming year. The workshop underscored CRESCENT’s function as a hub, connecting scientists and practitioners, translating research into actionable products, and catalyzing collaboration across jurisdictions and disciplines.

Suggested Citation

Clifford, A.E., Sahakian, V.J., Elizabeth, J., and Partnerships & Applications Workshop Participants (2025). Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center Partnerships & Applications Workshop, June 26-27, 2025 - Workshop Report. CRESCENT Open Documents Library. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17553977>

Introduction

The Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center (CRESCENT) was established as a National Science Foundation (NSF)-funded research program in October 2023.¹ The center's primary objective is to answer fundamental science questions about the Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ), the region of highest seismic risk for the USA and Canada. Through this research, CRESCENT's broader mission is to increase awareness and understanding of earthquake related hazards and move society toward greater resilience.

CRESCENT's structure includes a Partnerships & Applications (P&A) pillar that focuses on developing and maintaining relationships and facilitating ongoing communication between center scientists and external partners. These relationships are critical to ensure that the center's science products are relevant and applicable to resilience efforts. The annual Partnerships & Applications Workshop is the center's major forum for bringing the wider earthquake research and resilience community together in person and this report documents the second iteration of this event, held on 26-27 June 2025 at University of Oregon's NE Portland campus.

Workshop Overview

Workshop Purpose, Goals and Design

CRESCENT's inaugural Partnerships and Applications Workshop in June 2024 brought together participants from across the spectrum of communities concerned with Cascadia earthquake hazards resilience and research, including federal, state and local government agencies, policy makers, practitioners, educators, and the public at large.² The workshop served two main functions: (i) familiarizing the community with CRESCENT's structure and currently funded research objectives; and (ii) establishing the common challenges, needs, and areas for collaboration around CSZ hazards.

Discussions and survey responses from the 2024 workshop revealed four common challenges and a unified call for interorganizational coordination (Table 1).³ The planning committee used these findings to set the goals, themes and structure for the 2025 workshop agenda. In response to feedback from 2024, the 2025 workshop was extended to 1.5 days and an additional half day for optional field trips. (See Appendix 1 for the full agenda.)

¹ See <https://cascadiaquakes.org/>

² See <https://cascadiaquakes.org/2024/04/10/2024-partnerships-applications-workshop/>

³ Sahakian, V. J., Clifford, A. E., & Tate-Jones, M. K. (2025). Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center Partnerships & Applications Workshop, June 27, 2024 - Workshop Report. CRESCENT Open Documents Library. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14796929>

The 2025 workshop goals were to:

1. Foster bidirectional communication between CRESCENT scientists and the wider earthquake research/resilience community
2. Explore emergent themes of the 2024 workshop:
 - Science communication
 - Emergency preparedness and response planning
 - Data access and availability
 - Resource limitations
3. Facilitate interorganizational collaboration and coordination

Day one focused on building partnerships. An opening “Cascadia Connections” exercise asked participants to reflect on their current and ideal institutional relationships, with a view to better understanding the earthquake research ecosystem and associated communication pathways. A “Science to Practice Case Studies” panel session followed, demonstrating the importance of relationships in impactful resilience work. Daniel Eungard of the Washington Geological Survey discussed working with Elyssa Tappero of the Washington Emergency Management Division and coastal port operators to improve the state’s tsunami response planning. Mike Kortenhof of the Oregon Department of Environmental Quality and Ana Tijerina Esquino of Portland State University highlighted the cyclic “science to practice to science” approach that they have followed in addressing implementation of seismic design standards for critical fuels infrastructure in Oregon. Lisa Busch, former Executive Director of Sitka Sound Science Center and Oregon State University’s Annette Patton presented on their partnership between scientists and rural residents in a community led landslide forecasting project in Alaska.

The afternoon session provided science updates from CRESCENT’s Working and Special Interest Groups,⁴ and presentations from two of the center’s seed grant recipients: Brett Maurer (University of Washington) sharing his work on liquefaction hazard mapping using machine learning, and Andreas Plesch (Harvard University) demonstrating interoperability of the fault models generated by CRESCENT for the PNW and SCEC for California.⁵

The remainder of day one and morning of day two was dedicated to sessions exploring the common challenges identified in the 2024 workshop (Table 1): science communication challenges, the need for scenarios, the concept of a Cascadia data dashboard, and addressing workforce skills gaps/education opportunities. Each session was introduced with short presentations from different institutional perspectives, before participants moved into round table discussions to consider their own organizational needs, potential collaboration opportunities, and next steps.

The importance of interorganizational coordination was highlighted throughout the workshop and at a poster/digital media reception on the evening of the first day (Appendix

⁴ See <https://cascadiaquakes.org/science/>

⁵ See <https://cascadiaquakes.org/2024/07/16/2024-seed-grant-awards/>

2). Field trips to showcase local seismic hazard awareness and mitigation efforts on the afternoon of day two provided specific opportunities for making personal connections. The meeting closed with an individual reflection activity in which participants shared their top learning from the workshop and expressed aspirations for future collaboration (Appendix 3).

Table 1: Common needs and challenges identified by the seismic hazards community during the 2024 CRESCENT Partnerships & Applications Workshop

Overarching need: INTERORGANIZATIONAL COORDINATION	
SCIENCE COMMUNICATION & ENGAGEMENT unified messaging and plain language communication of earthquake science, hazards and uncertainties targeted to different audiences	EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS & RESPONSE PLANNING wider infrastructure redundancy and unified response planning across borders, jurisdictions and sectors
DATA AVAILABILITY & ACCESS centralized, navigable data sets, tailored to applications/end users	RESOURCE LIMITATIONS lack of funding, competing budget priorities, personnel and skill shortages

Participation and Representation

There were 127 registrants for the workshop. Most attended in person, while an online option allowed participation from a group of ~12 who were unable to travel. On day two, some participants from the annual meeting of the National Association of Geoscience Teachers (NAGT) Pacific Northwest Chapter joined the geoscience education and workforce opportunities discussion and participated in the afternoon field trips.⁶

An indication of representation is apparent from the post event survey in which 55 respondents reported their professional role and organization (Table 2).

Approximately a quarter of respondents identified as research scientists, with the other three quarters representing practitioner, governmental and educator roles. Academic institutions and state/local agencies had the most representatives with about a third of respondents identifying in each of these categories. Federal and tribal entities, public utilities, and private industry had lower representation, with 7% or less respondents in each of these categories.

⁶ See <https://nagt.org/nagt/sections/northwest/annualmeeting>

Table 2. Characteristics of Survey Respondents

Note: N = 55 responses

<p>What is your primary professional role? (mark only one)</p>	<p>20% Emergency Management 24% Research Scientist 6% Engineering, architecture 14% Educator or Extension Specialist 6% Student 2% Technician, staff member 6% Planning, Zoning, Regulatory 4% Post-doc 20% Other (specify): “Communications” “Community Safety Advocate, Neighborhood Emergency Team” “Consultant” “Network Instrumentation Engineer” “Operations Team Lead for Communication, Education, and Technical Engagement” “Pesticide Specialist” “Private industry – risk management” “Public Health” “Supporting school districts with safety planning” “Tribal”</p>
<p>Which terms best describe your organization? (mark all that apply)</p>	<p>27% State, regional or local agency 36% University offering related PhD degrees 6% Federal department, agency, or other federal entity 7% Nonprofit organization 4% Public utility 7% University offering related Masters (but not PhD) degrees 6% Private company or industry organization 6% Primarily undergraduate institution (PUI) 2% Minority-serving institution (MSI) -Historically Black College or University (HBCU) -Community College -High School or Middle School 6% Tribal organization 9% Other (specify): “CERT” “Consulting agency” “Network of professionals and organizations” “Seismic network” “Volunteer: Advocacy”</p>

Discussion Summaries

Each of the workshop sessions included time for cross-disciplinary discussion, with prompts provided to guide conversation. Summaries from written notes and group share-outs are provided below.

A. CASCADIA CONNECTIONS EXERCISE

Participants were invited to review an infographic displaying a classification of organizations involved in Cascadia earthquake research and resilience (Appendix 5). After making group edits and additions to the entities represented, individuals considered the partner relationships of their respective organizations, reflecting on both current and aspirational connections. Subsequent discussion focused on the level of representation of different organizational sectors and the areas for improved connection.

The exercise highlighted the following main concerns and priorities:

- Community organizations, schools (K-12 and higher ed), and media are underrepresented on the infographic. These local-level entities were identified as essential but often overlooked channels for reaching the public.
- Insurance industry and private sector risk modeling companies need to be better integrated into resilience planning. Establishing economic impacts can be a driver for policymaking and prioritizing investment in research and preparedness efforts.
- Siloing is a recurring problem. There were calls for better communication across jurisdictions (local, state, federal, cross-border U.S./Canada) and between sectors (science, policy, emergency management, community organizations) to increase consistency of messaging, minimize duplication of efforts, and improve collective action.
- The scale of response needed for a Cascadia event requires establishing clearer structures and expectations for interorganizational coordination and information flow. Scenarios and regional exercises were suggested as valuable tools for strengthening cross-sector and jurisdictional connections and to bridge the gap between science and practice.
- Durable funding and policy support is required for resilience efforts to be sustainable and impactful. Smaller communities are particularly resource-limited and are reliant on funded regional to national level partnerships.

B. SCIENCE TO PRACTICE REFLECTION

After presentations and a panel discussion of case studies that demonstrated successful science to practice partnerships, participants were asked to discuss the application of this approach to other facets of seismic hazard resilience. Practitioners with relevant subject matter expertise facilitated discussion groups on the following topics:

- Multi agency response planning
- Site responses to ground shaking
- Public awareness and preparedness
- Tsunami research, education and outreach needs
- Critical infrastructure resilience
- Community driven science

See Appendix 1 for list of facilitators and full topic descriptions.

The summaries below reflect groups’ consideration of each topic, including societal need, research priorities, and recommended next steps.

1. Multi-agency response planning: Enable rapid, coordinated disaster recovery that protects lives, property, and natural resources through effective multi-agency collaboration.

Table 3: Summary of research priorities and recommendations for multi-agency response planning

Research and Practice Priorities	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop interoperable, standardized data systems shared across agencies and disciplines. • Strengthen frameworks for multi-agency coordination, leadership clarity, and intergovernmental communication. • Map system and agency interdependencies to understand cascading effects. • Integrate technical, economic, and policy perspectives to move from assessment to mitigation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain up-to-date contact networks and run regular regional tabletop exercises. • Build stronger linkages between scientists, engineers, and emergency managers—translate data into timelines and recovery metrics. • Create consistent regional messaging (e.g., “Two Weeks Ready”) and a unified, public-facing alert/data platform modeled after wildfire systems (e.g. WatchDuty app). • Reduce silos through joint scenario planning that incorporates housing, health, and other cross-sector needs.

2. Site response and ground shaking: Turn seismic research into actionable, site-specific guidance for engineers, planners, and communities to enhance earthquake resilience.

Table 4: Summary of research priorities and recommendations for site response and ground shaking

Research and Practice Priorities	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Characterize Cascadia-specific ground motion, including long-duration shaking, basin effects, and soil–structure interaction. • Expand site-specific and basin-level instrumentation and data sharing. • Study how social media and communication networks influence understanding and response. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve data consistency and transparency across agencies and map products. • Translate technical information into plain language for non-specialist users. • Incentivize open data exchange and collaborative research culture. • Ensure equity by providing smaller and tribal communities with access to localized ground motion data. • Strengthen two-way communication channels between researchers, engineers, and end-users.

3. Public hazard awareness and preparedness: Build public understanding and encourage practical, inclusive preparedness actions before earthquakes and tsunamis.

Table 5: Summary of research priorities and recommendations for public hazard awareness & preparedness

Research and Practice Priorities	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study how people form mental models of earthquake risk and adaptive protective actions. • Test engagement formats that build long-term retention and behavioral readiness. • Identify techniques to leverage both the effectiveness of centralized and distributed information hubs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplify messaging: use visual, multilingual, and audience-specific materials. • Centralize information in one trusted hub linked to local resources. • Conduct listening sessions to understand community perceptions and tailor outreach. • Promote peer learning and storytelling over one-way expert communication. • Sustain engagement through annual drills (e.g., ShakeOut) and interactive community events.

4. Tsunami research, education, and outreach: Provide accurate, actionable tsunami guidance and coordinated response planning to protect coastal communities and ecosystems.

Table 6: Summary of research priorities and recommendations for tsunami research, education & outreach

Research and Practice Priorities	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model debris generation, transport, and cleanup logistics—including hazardous materials and limited staging areas. • Integrate sediment and debris transport modeling using remote sensing and national lab resources. • Understand communication dynamics between USGS (earthquake alerts) and NOAA (tsunami warnings). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish consistent, coordinated alert pathways between federal and local entities. • Tailor tsunami guidance for specific audiences—fishermen, mariners, port operators—avoiding one-size-fits-all messaging. • Proactively map coastal storage sites and material inventories for post-event cleanup. • Develop communication templates to explain small or atypical tsunamis quickly and clearly to the public.

5. Critical infrastructure: Safeguard essential lifelines—energy, water, transport, and communications—to minimize cascading failures and to accelerate recovery.

Table 7: Summary of research priorities and recommendations for tsunami research, education & outreach

Research and Practice Priorities	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map interdependencies among lifeline systems to identify cascading failure risks. • Update asset inventories and vulnerability maps to guide retrofits and response. • Study performance of infrastructure across varied soil and hazard conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build sustained partnerships between scientists, engineers, and operators to translate findings into action. • Support policy and funding mechanisms for retrofits and redundancy. • Encourage integrated planning across utilities and jurisdictions. • Use scenario-based exercises to prioritize restoration sequences and dependencies.

6. Community-driven science: Empower communities as co-creators of seismic resilience through trusted, participatory science.

Table 8: Summary of research priorities and recommendations for community-driven science

Research and Practice Priorities	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify effective models and scales of community–scientist partnerships. • Evaluate informal engagement (festivals, schools, museums) as mechanisms for science uptake. • Explore mechanisms to align research agendas with community-defined needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide pre-proposal funding to identify and articulate community research priorities. • Build partnerships with tribes, nonprofits, schools, churches, and industry. • Integrate community storytelling and cultural knowledge into scientific communication. • Prioritize long-term trust and shared ownership of data and outcomes over one-off engagement.

C. ADDRESSING SCIENCE COMMUNICATION CHALLENGES

Participants explored barriers, needs, and opportunities for improving the communication of seismic and hazard science to diverse audiences and moving from awareness to preparedness and collective resilience. Discussions emphasized the importance of trust, relationship-building, narrative framing, and consistent messaging across institutions and communities.

1. Barriers and opportunities

Table 9: Summary of science communication barriers and opportunities

Main Barriers	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust and credibility: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Many communities begin from a place of mistrust toward government or scientific institutions. – Scientists themselves often feel uncertain or anxious about public communication (“imposter syndrome”) and fear being misinterpreted. • Complexity and uncertainty: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Technical language, probabilistic data, and disciplinary jargon make it difficult to communicate clearly. – Uncertainty can undermine confidence or lead to apathy. • Message distortion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Media can sensationalize or oversimplify. Phrases like “in geological time” may be omitted, changing meaning. • Institutional and logistical constraints: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Different agency platforms, slow approval processes, departmental siloing, and inconsistent internal messaging delay communication. • Audience diversity: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build human connections and trust: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Show curiosity, humility, and emotion. – Admit uncertainty and emphasize shared values. – Empower trusted messengers – community leaders, educators, emergency managers, and tribal representatives – as primary communicators. • Storytelling: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Use lived experiences, place-based narratives, and mitigation success stories to make risk real and hopeful. – Scaffold information over time, tailoring complexity to audience needs. • Visuals and demonstrations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Use art, analogies, infographics, games, and hands-on activities to make abstract concepts tangible. • Unified voice:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cultural and experiential differences, trauma histories, and competing life priorities affect receptivity. – Normalcy bias, denial, and fatalism may limit engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Coordinated and intentional messaging from trusted institutions increases public confidence.
---	--

2. Potential areas and partners for research

Table 10: Summary of science communication research priorities and potential collaborators

Areas for Research	Recommended Collaborators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community trust networks: identify who the community already trusts and build genuine, sustained relationships with those individuals. • Audience interpretation: study how people perceive and emotionally respond to risk, uncertainty, and scientific information. • Motivation and learning: understand what inspires people to act on preparedness information. • Message simplification: learn how to convey uncertainty without losing accuracy or trust. • Co-creation of messages: explore partnerships with artists, educators, and social scientists to create accessible, visual, and narrative communication tools. • Platform dynamics: examine how different media and social channels amplify or distort scientific messages. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local leaders and trusted community representatives – including tribal elders, emergency managers, faith-based and civic leaders. • Social scientists and communicators – to bridge technical knowledge and human behavior. • Artists, educators, and media professionals – to create relatable, visual, and emotional engagement. • Youth and students – to extend awareness and normalize preparedness in future generations. • Institutional leaders and policymakers – to resource and support communication capacity. • Cross-disciplinary science teams – to align terminology and messaging across domains (earth science, engineering, social science, public health).

3. Recommendations and possible next steps

Table 11: Suggested next steps for the main recommendations from the science communication discussion

Recommendations	Possible Next Steps
Develop unified and trusted messaging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a “CRESCENT Communications Toolkit” with consistent visuals, key messages, and examples organized by theme and audience. • Establish a regional messaging framework to ensure consistent language and expectations across local, state, and federal levels.
Strengthen capacity and relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invest in train-the-trainer programs for community leaders, CERT teams, and educators. • Offer media and communication training for scientists, engineers, and technical staff. • Build ongoing relationships with communities beyond the project cycle; communication is sustained, not one-time.
Use storytelling and relatable framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect and share local and lived stories—contrasting successful and unsuccessful mitigation efforts—to foster relevance and hope. • Highlight how small, individual preparedness actions contribute to community resilience.

Advance research and innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborate on social science research to test message framing, trust dynamics, and behavioral outcomes. Experiment with creative formats (art, video, interactive media) to engage different audiences.
Sustain engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reinforce clear, simple messages through repeated, multi-channel outreach. Use community-approved communication and joint exercises (e.g., Great ShakeOut) to build familiarity and consistency.

D. CASCADIA SCENARIO NEEDS

The 2024 P&A workshop revealed a desire for more scenarios to aid preparedness and response planning. To better define this desire, participants were asked to discuss in small groups their perception of current scenario uses, needs, and gaps. The synthesis of responses is as follows:

1. Current and potential uses of scenarios

Participants described a wide range of applications for earthquake and multi-hazard scenarios, including:

- Risk and response planning – assessing hazards, potential damage, losses, and operational downtime; setting recovery priorities; guiding location- and time-specific evacuation and emergency response.
- Exercises and training – conducting tabletop and simulation exercises to practice communication, coordination, deployment, and unified response.
- Policy, education and outreach – using scenarios as a communication tool to bridge science, policy, and public understanding.

2. Scenario needs, gaps and limitations

Table 12: Summary of main scenario needs and limitations

Scenario Needs	Current Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multi-hazard and cascading events – scenarios should address aftershocks, fires, tsunamis, landslides, liquefaction, and other secondary hazards. Combined earthquake–tsunami scenarios – important for unified local and regional response planning (e.g., “move to high ground if strong shaking is felt”). Range of scenarios – provide lower, median, and worst-case options tailored for different audiences such as hospitals, schools, community centers, and the general public. Offering “worst case only” scenarios can lead to apathy or nihilism. Broader hazard scope – consider crustal fault and distant-source earthquakes in addition to Cascadia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Representation and participation – limited engagement of diverse stakeholders in drills and simulations. Critical infrastructure and data gaps – inconsistent treatment of infrastructure functionality (e.g., CEI Hub), and a lack of integration of satellite data, financial data, and decision-making frameworks. Communication and visualization – need for clearer storytelling of impacts and lived experiences, through visuals, narration, curricula, or interactive games. Data management – more emphasis on collecting, preserving, and sharing data,

<p>events, which can allow more time for actionable responses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applied integration – link scenarios to early warning and alert systems, staff training, community preparedness programs, and data collection efforts. • Collaborative use – support exercises and tabletop activities with multiple partners at the table. 	<p>including dashboards and tools for managing live data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realism and uncertainty – current scenarios simplify complex realities across the Cascadia Subduction Zone. Challenges include capturing the diversity of geography and jurisdictions, the uncertainties inherent in hazard modeling, and the chaotic nature of lived experiences during disaster and recovery.
---	---

E. BUILDING A CASCADIA DATA DASHBOARD

Responding to the data availability challenge identified from the 2024 workshop, this discussion focused on the vision for a Cascadia Data Dashboard that could connect, organize, and make accessible the wide range of data needed for understanding and planning around Cascadia Subduction Zone hazards. Participants emphasized the importance of consistent data standards, clear audience definitions, and long-term sustainability to ensure the dashboard’s usefulness and longevity.

1. Data needs and design parameters

Participants strongly supported a regional approach that builds on existing systems rather than duplicating them. The group envisioned a dashboard that integrates and links to state and federal databases while maintaining a consistent user experience and shared data standards across jurisdictions. Participants repeatedly emphasized that defining the intended audiences (e.g., scientists, engineers, emergency managers, educators, or the general public) is critical to determining both the level of detail and the interface design for any dashboard. Other themes and suggestions are summarized in the following table.

Table 13: Summary of design considerations and recommended actions for a Cascadia data dashboard

Design Consideration	Recommendations
Consistency and interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a unified data schema, symbology, and naming conventions across states. • Encourage coordination to ensure seamless integration of datasets.
Use and amplify existing resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build on established platforms such as state geologic databases and leverage CRESCENT’s role to host or link niche datasets not currently maintained elsewhere. • Develop a centralized “data availability” portal that links to repositories, metadata, and licensing information. • Improve Google search visibility to promote reputable, validated sources.
Tiered data products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer different levels of information—from raw data (Level 1) to interpreted products (Level 2) to scenario-based tools (Level 3)—to meet the needs of scientists, engineers, planners, emergency managers, educators, and the public.

Breadth of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include fault and paleoseismic data, subsurface and borehole information, landslide, liquefaction, and flooding hazards, infrastructure impacts, and cascading hazard layers. • Incorporate relevant social science, financial, and demographic data.
User experience and accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design for usability with features such as adjustable visual layers, color-blind friendly palettes, readable text, and “power user” modes for experts. • Consider AI-guided navigation or prompts to simplify complex datasets. • Use photos, historical imagery, and case studies to make data relatable and tangible. • Incorporate design and communication experts to ensure visual clarity and appeal.
Metadata and documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide comprehensive metadata including accuracy, reliability, update history, and source citations. • Define ownership and maintenance responsibilities for each dataset.
Sustainability and governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a clear plan for long-term maintenance and data transfer if funding or hosting changes. • Explore partnerships with USGS and/or state agencies for continuity.

2. Recommendations for Next Steps and Collaborations

Table 14: Suggested next steps and collaborators for development of a Cascadia data dashboard

Suggested Next Steps	Recommended Collaborators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define user audiences and functional tiers for dashboard products. • Convene a cross-agency planning meeting to align goals, data standards, and hosting responsibilities. • Develop a data governance and sustainability plan addressing long-term maintenance, funding continuity, and potential end-of-life transitions. • Establish metadata and interoperability standards to ensure consistency and data integrity across states. • Advance data literacy initiatives to help diverse users interpret and apply available data. • Engage design and communication professionals early to create a trusted, intuitive, and visually effective interface. • Plan for data archiving or transferability to ensure continuity beyond project cycles. • Explore AI-assisted features to improve accessibility, usability, and audience targeting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State and federal agencies: DOGAMI, USGS, state geological surveys (WA, OR, CA), state Departments of Transportation, and emergency management offices. • Design and technical experts: UI/UX design firms (e.g., Weiden & Kennedy), GIS professionals, and visualization specialists. • Academic and community partners: CRESCENT researchers, universities, educators, and science communication organizations such as OMSI. • Applied and private-sector collaborators: realtors, infrastructure agencies, and data platforms with wide public reach (e.g., PortlandMaps.com). • Cross-disciplinary user groups: promote dialogue among geologists, engineers, fire specialists, social scientists, and emergency responders to ensure the dashboard reflects diverse data needs and practical applications.

F. ADDRESSING SKILLS GAPS, TRAINING NEEDS AND GEOSCIENCES EDUCATION OPPORTUNITIES

The 2024 workshop highlighted “resource limitations” as a shared challenge across the research and resilience community. The organizing committee chose to focus this discussion session on skills limitations rather than other resources (i.e. funding, equipment and personnel) given that CRESCENT has most potential to affect change in this area. Participants were asked to consider skills gaps, education opportunities, and recommendations for collaborations.

1. Skills gaps and education opportunities

Participants identified widespread skills gaps across the geoscience, engineering, and emergency management disciplines. Many gaps reflect the interdisciplinary nature of hazard analysis and the disconnect between academic preparation and applied practice. To bridge these gaps, participants noted the importance of combining formal instruction with applied experiences and integrated technical, field-based, and communication training. Including online and hybrid teaching models to reach diverse learners and working professionals was also recommended.

Table 15: Summary of earthquake hazard research & resilience workforce skills needs and opportunities

Skills Gaps and Challenges	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interdisciplinary and professional skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Engineers often lack geoscience background, and geoscientists lack engineering and project management exposure. – Gaps persist in plain-language communication, media literacy, ethics, and systems thinking. – There’s growing need for AI literacy and critical thinking to balance technological tools with judgment. ● Balancing need for field vs. technical skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Traditional field skills are declining while coding and data processing skills are increasingly essential. ● Local workforce capacity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Local and tribal governments often lack in-house geotechnical or hazard mapping expertise, relying on costly external specialists. – Adjunct teaching positions and low pay also limit local training capacity. ● "Perception problem": <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Geology is poorly represented in K–12 education - need more effective public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Curriculum integration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Combine fieldwork, coding, ethics, and project management within degree programs. – Offer cross-listed or team-taught courses bridging engineering, business, and geoscience. ● AI and communication training: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Incorporate communication, media literacy, and AI literacy into curricula to build adaptable, effective communicators. ● Experiential and project-based learning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Expand opportunities for community-engaged and scenario-based learning, internships, and collaborative projects with agencies. ● Early exposure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Promote earth science and teamwork skills in high school to strengthen pipelines into geoscience fields. ● Professional development: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Support continuing education and certification (e.g., Association of State

<p>outreach to promote geoscience as a rewarding, socially relevant career.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barriers to participation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Students face challenges with cost, access to field camps, math requirements, and confidence (impostor syndrome). These contribute to low enrollment and retention, particularly among underrepresented groups. 	<p>Boards of Geology review sessions, online technical courses).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Offer funding or tuition support for emergency management staff pursuing geoscience coursework.
---	--

2. Recommended collaborative actions

Collaboration across disciplines, institutions, and communities was viewed as essential to overcoming limited staffing, funding, and instructional capacity. Suggestions included:

Table 16: Summary of earthquake hazard research & resilience workforce skills needs and opportunities

Suggested collaboration	Recommended action
Cross-institutional teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • encourage shared teaching models where practicing engineers or professionals lead applied courses, and geoscientists contribute to engineering programs.
Resource sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase visibility of free or open training materials (e.g., GIS resources via OpenTopography, EarthScope, CRESCENT webinars). • develop a central repository for educational and technical materials.
Agency–academia partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strengthen partnerships with federal, state, and local agencies to support internships, applied research, and training. • integrate students into real-world scenario exercises.
Community and tribal engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collaborate with tribal nations to co-develop locally relevant geoscience training programs and respect tribal governance and educational priorities.
Interdisciplinary convenings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • continue convening educators, practitioners, and researchers (e.g., CRESCENT/CLIP webinars) to share best practices and address resource gaps collectively.
Communication partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collaborate with communication and psychology experts to improve science communication training and produce accessible, audience-focused materials.

Next Steps

It is clear from participant engagement, the workshop discussion summaries, and evaluation responses (Appendix 4) that collective progress is being made in the earthquake research and resilience space. Motivation is high, though much work remains to be done. The challenge for CRESCENT is in identifying where the center can be most impactful in the short-term with its current structure and resources, while being cognizant of opportunities for longer-term funding and an increased scope for research products and services. Table 17 (below) reflects action items for CRESCENT P&A in response to the priorities gleaned from the workshop discussions and conversations with partner organizations:

Table 17. Summary of next steps for each of the main workshop themes

Theme/Session	CRESCENT actions/next steps
INTERORGANIZATIONAL COLLABORATION Cascadia Connections Exercise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct networking and outreach to increase representation of local, tribal, and private-sector partners on the partnership map of Cascadia resilience organizations • Create and maintain an online, updateable version of the map • Continue to invite cross-jurisdictional, cross sector representation at CRESCENT events, activities, and committees • Consider future activities and uses of the map within the academic community to increase awareness of contextualizing research within the hazards and resilience space
SCIENCE COMMUNICATION AND ENGAGEMENT Addressing Science Communication Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue to build engagement and facilitate coordination with hazard and resilience communicators. • Reinforce clear, simple messages through repeated, multi-channel outreach from trusted authorities. • Use community-approved communication and joint exercises (e.g., Great ShakeOut) to build familiarity and consistency. • Continue to pursue collaborations between practitioners (partners in science communication), and social scientists.
EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS & RESPONSE PLANNING Cascadia Scenario Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use all available forums to engage with researchers, practitioners, planners and policymakers to get continued input on the needs and potential contributions of organizations toward development of boundary and jurisdiction crossing scenarios. • Make scenario development and curation a central theme of the 2026 P&A Workshop and convene a planning committee with multi-sector representation from across Cascadia. • Pursue funding and pilot studies for scenario development.
DATA AVAILABILITY AND ACCESS Cascadia Data Dashboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop an online version of the Cascadia Connections map as a directory style dashboard with links to key datasets, products, and resources for each organization represented. • Convene a data dashboard advisory group to oversee development and give interim feedback.
RESOURCE LIMITATIONS Addressing Skills Gaps, Training Needs, and Geoscience Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider developing a repository for educational/technical materials. • Inform 2026 seed grant criteria with partner resource limitation considerations, and disseminate application resources and information to partners.

2025-26 Priorities

The Cascadia Connections Map and scenario development actions look to be worthy immediate objectives for CRESCENT P&A. Workshop participants see the Cascadia Connections Map as a valuable, scalable visualization for building relationships, training staff, informing strategy, and promoting community engagement. Recommendations to make the map interactive, accessible, and a living, regularly updated tool for collaboration and coordination across the Cascadia resilience community are a solid basis for developing a prototype this year.

The need for scenarios and interorganizational exercises for preparedness and response spanned many of the discussion sessions. A deeper consideration of this topic is clearly necessary and it seems prudent to make this a central theme for the 2026 P&A workshop. Planning should include formulation of a strategy for how the community may be able to fund and contribute to the development and compilation of a suite of scenarios, as well as identifying and discussing the wide spectrum of needs that have been shared.

Acknowledgements

This workshop was funded as a Major Activity of CRESCENT under NSF cooperative agreement #2225286. NSF bears no responsibility for design or implementation of the workshop.

The Partnerships & Applications 2025 Workshop Planning Committee includes:

Andy Clifford CRESCENT P&A Program Manager, **Valerie Sahakian** CRESCENT P&A Program Lead, **Amanda Erickson** CRESCENT Office Coordinator, **Tiegan Hobbs** Natural Resources Canada, **Carrie Garrison-Laney** Washington Sea Grant, **Ian Stone** United States Geological Survey, **Ali Burgos** Cascadia Coastline and Peoples Hub, and **Ellen Peters** University of Oregon

Thanks also for the participation and guidance of the CRESCENT Partnerships & Applications Committee (PAC): **Lori Dengler** Cal Poly Humboldt, **Michael Olsen** Oregon State University, **Rob Witter** USGS, **Pieter-Ewald Share** Oregon State University, and **alex grant** USGS.

The planning committee and PAC are grateful to all presenters and facilitators (listed in Appendix 1) and for support and contributions from the following:

- The UO NE Portland Event Team
- UO Print Services and Travel
- Oregon Hazards Lab (OHAZ)
- Kam and Kam Catering
- The Raddison PDX Airport Hotel
- Pacific Gas & Electric Company
- United States Geological Survey, Earthscope, SCEC, Cascadia Coastlines and Peoples (CoPes) Hub
- CRESCENT Senior personnel and CRESCENT staff
- Micheal Coe, Cedar Lake Research Group LLC
- Kellum Tate-Jones Refugium Consulting LLC
- Daina Hardisty, Mt Hood Community College/NAGT
- Yumei Wang, Portland State University

Generative AI was used in the compilation of notes for the discussion summaries.

Appendices

Appendix I – Workshop Agenda

Thursday, June 26

8:00 am: Workshop check-in and coffee break

8:30 am: Opening remarks *presented by Valerie Sahakian*, CRESCENT, Partnerships and Applications Lead and **Andy Clifford**, CRESCENT, Partnerships & Applications Manager

8:45 am: Cascadia connections exercise – mapping interorganizational connectivity and communications pathways *introduced by Valerie Sahakian*, CRESCENT, Partnerships and Applications Lead

9:45 am: Coffee break

10:05 am: Science to practice case studies – panel presentations and Q&A

- “From Models to Mitigation: How Tsunami Maritime Resilience Projects Provide a Safe Harbor for Partnership Discussions” *presented by Daniel Eungard*, Washington Geological Survey and **Elyssa Tappero**, Washington Emergency Management Division
- “Fuel Resilience in Cascadia: Bridging Science, Policy, and Practice in Oregon” *presented by Mike Kortenhof*, Oregon Department of Environmental Quality and **Ana Tijerina Esquino**, Portland State University
- “Community Partnerships for Understanding Landslides in Southeast Alaska” *presented by Lisa Busch*, Southeast Alaska Landslide Information and Preparedness Partnership and **Annette Patton**, Oregon State University

11:00 am: Science to practice - roundtable discussion session

Multi agency response planning

Large earthquakes and tsunamis are infrequent and societally impactful events requiring the coordination of government agencies, emergency responders, infrastructure operators, trusted community leaders, and the geoscience and engineering communities to plan for and respond to such events. This Science-to-Practice session invites workshop attendees across all disciplines to participate in a discussion about earthquake and tsunami response planning with a focus on ensuring that these groups are better coordinated and therefore more effective in their respective areas of responsibility following a major event. *Led by Tim Dawson*, Seismic Hazards Program Manager, California Geological Survey

Site responses to ground shaking/behavior

During a Cascadia Subduction Zone earthquake, we can expect extended ground shaking for one to three minutes, with the highest intensities along the coast and strong shaking well inland. Areas with soft soils may experience site responses like amplified shaking and ground failures from liquefaction. This discussion will address questions around impacts of these responses on vulnerable structures. *Led by Jay Wilson*, Resilience Coordinator, Clackamas County Disaster Management

Public awareness and preparedness

What are potential approaches to collaboration between researchers and practitioners that will yield tangible products and programs that have an immediate impact on informing and promoting public safety? This roundtable discussion dives into how CRESCENT can potentially operationalize its third overarching goal in its mission statement. *Co-led by Robert deGroot*, Coordinator for Communication, Education, Outreach, and Technical Engagement, ShakeAlert® Earthquake Early Warning System and **Dare Baldwin**, Professor, University of Oregon

Ongoing tsunami research, education and outreach needs

At this roundtable, we will discuss potential areas of tsunami research needed to support tsunami hazard education and outreach. This may include identifying research that will improve tsunami hazard planning, public safety, or future education and outreach efforts. *Led by Carrie Garrison-Laney*, Coastal Hazards Specialist & NOAA Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory Liaison, Washington Sea Grant

Critical infrastructure resilience

Services from lifeline systems (water, wastewater, electric power, natural gas, petroleum fuel, communications and transportation, including roads, rail, airports and ports) are needed for everyday purposes and for disaster response and recovery. Urgent priorities—spanning from sectors and specific facilities to research and policy gaps—will be covered. *Led by Yumei Wang*, Senior Advisor on Infrastructure Resilience and Risk, Portland State University

Community driven science

Community driven science includes many of the same elements it takes to build a strong friendship, a business partnership or any good relationship. This theme table will discuss some of ways to build meaningful community partnerships involving scientific discovery. *Led by Lisa Busch*, Director, Southeast Alaska Landslide Information and Preparedness Partnership

Multi agency planning (ZOOM Room)

Led by Tiegan Hobbs, Research Scientist / Adjunct Professor, Geological Survey of Canada / The University of British Columbia / University of Victoria

12:00 pm: Lunch (1st Floor of Campus Center)

1:15 pm: CRESCENT presentations

Working Group presentations

- Community Fault Model (CFM) *presented by Becky Fildes*, Postdoctoral Researcher, Western Washington University
- Community Velocity Model (CVM) *presented by Pieter Share*, Assistant Professor, Oregon State University

- Coupling, Seismicity, Slow Slip (C3S) *presented by* **Brendan Crowell**, Assistant Professor, The Ohio State University
- Dynamic rupture, Earthquake cycles, Tsunami models (DET) *presented by* **Brittany Erickson**, Associate Professor, University of Oregon
- Cascadia Paleoseismology (CPAL) *presented by* **David Bruce**, Postdoctoral Researcher, Virginia Tech

Special Interest Group presentations

- Offshore Observations *presented by* **Jianhua Gong**, Assistant Professor, Indiana University
- Cascading Hazards *presented by* **Ben Leshchinsky**, Professor, Oregon State, University
- Ground Motion Modeling *presented by* **Valerie Sahakian**, Associate Professor, University of Oregon
- Cascadia Subduction Fluids *presented by* **Pieter Share**, Assistant Professor, Oregon State University

Seed Grant presentations

- “Cascadia Liquefaction Hazard Maps for Scenario Planning and Rapid Response: Partnering Around Community Data and Mechanics-Informed AI” *presented by* **Brett Maurer**, University of Washington
- “Enhancing interoperability between the SCEC and CRESCENT Community Fault Models” *presented by* **Andreas Plesch**, Harvard University

2:30 pm: Coffee break with opportunity to see CVM/CFM viewers on TVs in the room

3:00 pm: Addressing science communication challenges – workshop session *led by* **Ellen Peters**, Professor, University of Oregon and **Maxwell Ely**, Program Manager, University of Oregon

Roundtable discussion session themes and facilitators:

- **Tailoring messaging: knowing your audience and timing**
Wendy Bohon, California Geological Survey
Tiegan Hobbs, Geological Survey of Canada
- **Building trust: cultivating communication pathways**
Lisa Busch, Central Council Tlingit and Haida Indian Tribes of Alaska
Bill Steele, Pacific Northwest Seismic Network
- **Overcoming fear/helplessness: empowering preparedness action**
Laura Hall, Regional Disaster Preparedness Organization
- **Making earthquakes relevant: storytelling and engaging your audience**
Bob de Groot, United States Geological Survey
Liz Safran, Lewis & Clark College
- **Conveying complexity and uncertainty: educating your audience**
Kelly Missett, OHAZ, University of Oregon
Daniel Eungard, Washington Geological Survey
- **Training communicators: who, what, how?**

Dare Baldwin, University of Oregon

Gabriel Lotto, Pacific Northwest Seismic Network

- **Agency coordination and unified messaging** (ZOOM Room)

David Snider, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

Lori Dengler, Cal Poly Humboldt

4:30 pm: Poster/digital media presentations and light appetizer reception with cash bar (1st Floor of Campus Center)

6:00 pm: Workshop Adjourns

Friday, June 27

8:00 am: Registration and coffee

8:30 am: Welcome and introduction to day 2

8:40 am: Addressing Cascadia earthquake scenario needs – workshop session with introductory presentations:

- “Broad needs for earthquake scenarios and the Canadian perspective” *presented by Tiegan Hobbs*, Geological Survey of Canada
- “Why produce earthquake scenarios?” *presented by Katherine Scharer*, United States Geological Survey
- “Use of earthquake scenarios for risk evaluation” *presented by Albert Kottke*, Pacific Gas and Electric Company

9:35 am: Building a Cascadia data dashboard – workshop session with introductory presentations:

- “Towards a Cascadia Subduction Zone Datahub: Framework and considerations” *presented by Lydia Staisch*, United States Geological Survey
- “The Washington Geological Survey Data Portal: What is it, Why do we have it, and How could it relate to CRESCENT initiatives?” *presented by Megan Anderson*, Washington Geological Survey
- “Cascadia Lifelines Program (CLiP): Data to the Rescue” *presented by Michael Olsen*, Oregon State University

10:30 am: Break

10:45 am: Addressing skills gaps, training needs and geosciences education opportunities – workshop session (in collaboration with NAGT) with introductory presentations:

- “CRESCENT and the Workforce of the Future” *presented by Andrew Meigs*, Oregon State University
- “A Brief Introduction to the National Association of Geoscience Teachers” *presented by Daina Hardisty*, Mount Hood Community College/ NAGT
- “Enhancing Earthquake Risk Reduction through Professional Development” *presented by Amanda McHale*, Oak Ridge Associated Universities

11:45 pm: Closing remarks

12:00 pm: Lunch and briefing for optional field trips

1:00 pm: Optional field trips (in collaboration with NAGT)

Option 1: Seismic risk and resilience at the Critical Energy Infrastructure Hub and Port of Portland Marine Terminal

This field trip will visit sites along the Willamette River in North Portland for views of the Critical Energy Infrastructure Hub and Port of Portland Marine Terminal. Learn from subject matter experts and engage in discussion around seismic risk and resilience efforts at these locations.

Option 2: Seismic risk and resilience for critical infrastructure in NE Portland

This field trip will visit sites along the Columbia River in Northeast Portland for a close view of the Levees and Port of Portland Airport. Learn from subject matter experts and engage in discussion around seismic risk and resilience efforts at these locations.

Option 3: Models and tools for advancing community preparedness at Oregon Museum of Science and Industry (OMSI)

How can you engage your community in conversations about earthquake awareness and preparedness? Learn about event models like ShakeOut with potential to reach large number of community members, explore how tools like Raspberry Shake can support education and outreach, and get hands-on with demos that foster two-way conversations with people of diverse ages and backgrounds.

Appendix 2 – Poster and Digital Media Presentations

POSTERS

Table A1: Posters presented on 1st Floor of Campus Center

#	Authors	Title
1	Katrina Arras, et al.	“ShakeAlert Ready Schools Provides Resources to Integrate Earthquake Early Warning into School Communities”
2	Mary Grace Bato, et al.	“The OPERA Displacement Product: Overview and Application”
3	Marge Belcastro, Ashley Streig, Jazzy M Graham-Davis	“Refining Cascadia subduction zone earthquake timing in Netarts Bay, Oregon, with new age dating from a ghost forest tree and marsh stratigraphy”
4	Marcie Benne et al.	“Advancing Community Resilience with the EPIcenter Partnership”
5	Lori Dengler	“The December 5, 2024 M7.0 Earthquake and the Problem of Tweener Tsunami Warnings”
6	Daniel Eungard	“Washington Geological Survey: Tsunami hazard modeling & real-world applications”
7	Laura Gabel, Jonathan Allan, Fletcher O’Brien	“Beat the Wave! Exploring tsunami evacuation difficulty and mitigation options through GIS modeling”
8	Shubharoop Ghosh	“TsunamiCat: Tsunami Loss Estimation Platform for Scenario-based and Probabilistic Risk Assessment”

9	Cait Goodwin and Felicia Olmeta Schult	“Tsunami Quests: Self-guided outdoor hunts designed to increase situational awareness”
10	Laura Hall	“Collaboration & Resilience Building in the Portland Metro Region”
11	Grant Kelly	“How Big is Too Big? The Tipping Point of Systemic Failure”
12	Kelly Missett	“The Oregon Hazards Lab: Building a Statewide Platform for Multi-Hazards Monitoring and Alerting”
13	Elizabeth Safran, et al.	“Playing with Disaster: Interactive Digital Media as Research and Outreach Tools”
14	Cole M. Speed, et al.	“A global archive of accessible, analysis-ready coseismic displacement products for earthquake science applications derived from SAR and optical datasets”
15	Ana Tijerina Esquino	“Fuel Tank Seismic Stability in Oregon, an overview of findings from Seismic Vulnerability Assessments”
16	Elizabeth Van Boskirk, et al.	“Network of the Americas (NOTA) GNSS, Borehole Strainmeter, and Seismic Data Links and Tools”

Table A2: Posters presented in Room 212, 2nd Floor of Campus Center

#	Authors	Title
1	Brendan Crowell, et al.	“C3S: Mapping Cascadia’s Fault Slip Processes”
2	Tina Dura, et al.	“The Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center (CRESCENT) Cascadia Paleoseismology Working Group (CPAL)”
3	Brittany A. Erickson, Eric M. Dunham and Alice Gabriel	“CRESCENT Dynamic Rupture, Earthquake and Tsunami (DET) Modeling”
4	Rebecca Fildes, et al.	“CRESCENT CFM: Building a Community Fault Model for the Cascadia Subduction Zone System”
5	Jianhua Gong	“High-Resolution Earthquake Catalog Reveals Complex Fault Network in Southern Cascadia from Amphibious Seismic Array”
6	Bin He, et al.	“CRESCENT Generation 0 Community Velocity Model: Bayesian joint inversion of phase velocity and receiver functions”
7	Craig Nichol	“The National Association of Geoscience Teachers: Earth Education for All”

DIGITAL MEDIA

Presented on 1st Floor of Campus Center:

“How to use OPERA DISP-S1 products” *presented by* M Grace Bato, Jet Propulsion Laboratory

“Stop the Spill” *presented by* Nancy Hiser, Linnton Neighborhood Association-Tank the Tanks

“Decision support for post-disaster recovery operations” *presented by* Joseph Louis, Oregon State University

“The Distant, Immersive, Virtual Education for Ocean Literacy (DIVE4OL) Virtual Reality app” and “Preparing for the Cascadia Subduction Zone Event - online course”, Glenda Hyde et al, OSU Extension, *presented by* Felicia Olmeta Schult, Oregon Sea Grant/OSU Extension

“Playing with Disaster: Interactive Digital Media as Research and Outreach Tools”
presented by Elizabeth Safran, Erik Nilsen, Peter Drake, and Bryan Sebok, Lewis & Clark College

“Data repository; ‘A global one-stop shop of coseismic displacement products’” *presented by* Cole Speed, Jet Propulsion Laboratory

Presented in Room 212, 2nd Floor of Campus Center:

"CVM webviewer" *presented by* Pieter-Ewald Share

“CPAL Paleoseismic Database” *presented by* David Bruce and Lydia Staisch

“CFM webviewer and products” *presented by* Rebecca Fildes

Appendix 3 – Reflection Activity Responses

In the closing session participants were asked to write anonymous responses to the following prompts on index cards that were collected at the end of the workshop (summarized in Table A3 and A4):

- “My key workshop learning”
- “A potential collaboration I am going to follow up on...”

Table A3: Summary of main learning themes and takeaways from reflection activity responses

Main learning theme	Specific takeaways
Communication & science translation	<p>Communication is both a strength and a major gap. Need to balance technical detail with simplicity. Science and engineering research is too disconnected from emergency management and planning. Practitioners want information curated in a usable way. Many comments on Ellen Peters’ session—effective communication of data, numbers, and motivation. Disconnect between scientists’ assumptions and emergency managers’ needs. Messaging must be audience-specific (tribal communities, pilots, contractors, general public).</p>
Partnerships and community engagement	<p>Partnership (vs. stakeholder) framing is critical. Trust-building and long-term relationships are essential. Appreciation for sessions on local/tribal partnerships. Partnerships strengthen outcomes and open new opportunities. Need more inclusivity, peer-to-peer relationships, and cross-community connections. Interest in CRESCENT serving as a clearinghouse or hub.</p>
Networking and collaboration	<p>Broad interest in connecting across disciplines and agencies. Many noted the size, diversity, and passion of this community. Importance of interdisciplinary approaches—scientists, engineers, planners, emergency managers, educators. Desire to continue collaboration beyond the workshop. Recognized shared goals but also shared frustrations—CRESCENT seen as a vehicle to move forward.</p>

Awareness of data and resources	<p>Surprised by the volume of work already happening (need more advertising/outreach).</p> <p>Large number of tools, data, and resources available but often siloed.</p> <p>Interest in dashboards, hazard portals, and databases.</p> <p>More deterministic earthquake scenarios needed (not just worst-case).</p> <p>Tsunami forecasts and modeling seen as highly valuable to new audiences.</p>
Inspiration, hope, and motivation	<p>Many participants left feeling hopeful and energized.</p> <p>Recognition of the “brilliance” in the community and potential collective impact.</p> <p>Gratitude for exposure to new perspectives, resources, and opportunities.</p> <p>Value in simply gathering and connecting.</p>
Challenges and gaps	<p>Persistent gaps in science communication, diversity, education, and funding.</p> <p>Disconnects between fields (science ↔ practice, emergency management ↔ research).</p> <p>Workforce development challenges (training, university barriers, AI/information overload).</p> <p>Local agencies’ reliance on contractors may complicate trust and scenario use.</p> <p>Need for more cross-border, cross-discipline coordination.</p>
CRESCENT-specific learnings	<p>Interest in CRESCENT working groups, tools, and projects.</p> <p>Need for clearer understanding of what CRESCENT is and how to engage.</p> <p>Seen as a needed space and potential hub/clearinghouse.</p> <p>Opportunities for CRESCENT to advance science literacy in the PNW.</p>

Table A4: Summary of main collaboration interests from reflection activity responses

Collaboration themes	Specific interests
Earthquake and hazard scenario development	<p>Strong interest in developing, sharing, and applying earthquake scenarios for tabletop exercises, emergency management training, and planning (e.g., CEI Hub, Lower Mainland, tribal and local government use).</p> <p>Several plan to collaborate across disciplines (geoscientists, emergency managers, planners) and agencies (USGS, state departments, universities) to coordinate scenario data, approaches, and messaging across state and national borders.</p> <p>Calls for deterministic and practical scenario products that reflect real operational needs.</p>
Science communication and public engagement	<p>Widespread enthusiasm for joint science communication projects with CRESCENT, OMSI, Ellen Peters, Oregon Sea Grant, and others.</p> <p>Plans include developing outreach materials (posters, infographics, games, webinars, VR simulations) and training sessions on risk communication and public understanding of geoscience.</p> <p>Interest in linking communication research (e.g., University of Oregon, Oregon State University, Lewis & Clark, JPL/OPERA) with hands-on community education such as ShakeAlert Ready programs and museum collaborations.</p>
Data sharing and integration	<p>Many intend to collaborate on data sharing, formatting, and integration— notably with the CFM viewer, earthquake catalog, WA DNR geologic data portal, and CRESCENT’s planned dashboards.</p> <p>Opportunities identified for cross-agency coordination of metadata, schema, and data standards to enable seamless use across jurisdictions.</p>

	Some new partnerships focused on specialized datasets (radiocarbon specimens, fault databases, liquefaction mapping, OPERA satellite data).
Education, training and workforce development	Interest in creating new curricula and training programs, such as “Geohazards for EM 101,” and adding hazard preparedness content to university and trade programs. Plans for guest lectures, student field trips, and internship placements to engage early-career professionals. Shared goal of strengthening geoscience literacy and capacity in emergency management, schools, and communities.
Institutional and cross-sector partnerships	Collaborations between universities, agencies, and community organizations—especially CRESCENT, OMSI, USGS, Oregon Sea Grant, WA DNR, JPL/OPERA, and local/state emergency management offices. Expanding engagement with tribal communities, local governments, ports, utilities, and infrastructure operators (e.g., PDX, Pacific Power, Bureau of Reclamation). Recognition that these multi-sector partnerships are essential for integrated resilience planning and public trust.
Strengthening the CRESCENT network	Many plan to stay engaged with CRESCENT’s working groups, seed grants, and communication research. CRESCENT is viewed as a central hub for collaboration, connection, and resource exchange. Participants emphasized maintaining contact between workshops and expanding outreach to new audiences and underrepresented partners.

Appendix 4 – Evaluation Responses

A formal evaluation was conducted via a Qualtrics survey emailed to participants during the week following the workshop. This was completed by 55 participants. In addition to gathering feedback on efficacy of the workshop and suggestions for future iterations, the evaluation included questions to augment notes compiled from the discussion sessions. The evaluation questions and summaries of responses are provided below.

Did the sessions address the workshop themes of science communication, emergency preparation and response, data access, and resource limitations? Do you have suggestions for further exploration of these themes?

Most participants agreed that the workshop successfully addressed the intended themes, also emphasizing the need for their continued exploration and inclusion of more applied or interactive elements. The main suggestions included seeking greater involvement of emergency managers and resilience officers, developing scenario-based exercises, and showcasing demos of how partners such as utilities and infrastructure providers can apply CRESCENT data. Participants also requested more hands-on training in science communication, including practical exercises in simplifying technical content, case studies of successful outreach, and modeling of plain-language approaches. See Table A5 for more detailed recommendations.

Table A5: Summary of themes and recommendations for future workshops from evaluation responses

Theme / Focus Area	Recommendations/preferences for future workshops
Emergency preparation and response	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicate more time to emergency management, preparedness, and response applications. • Include emergency managers (EMs), resilience officers, and state commission chairs in planning and panels. • Conduct scenario-based exercises simulating post-event conditions (e.g., “what happens 1 hour to 1 year after a Cascadia event”). • Explore cross-sector coordination (utilities, airports, agencies) and how they use CRESCENT data to build resilience.
Science communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer hands-on or practical training sessions where participants practice communication skills (e.g., simplifying maps, using plain language, audience modeling). • Include case studies or mini-presentations on innovative communication methods from different organizations. • Model best practices in presentation materials (avoid jargon, use readable graphics and titles). • Continue to explore bridging the gap between scientists and public audiences, possibly through mentoring or paired discussion formats.
Interdisciplinary collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase real examples of multi-disciplinary projects that integrate subject-matter experts across fields. • Include discussions on how to connect research, policy, and community needs. • Address how CRESCENT can translate science into public safety outcomes through partnerships beyond academia (e.g., local governments, infrastructure agencies).
Data access and integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide interactive demonstrations or “data labs” using tools like DesignSafe. • Create a centralized website or dashboard compiling CRESCENT data resources and workshop outputs. • Offer hands-on activities to teach how to find, interpret, and apply available datasets.
Workshop design & participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain inclusive, discussion-based formats— participants valued hearing diverse perspectives. • Consider adding lightning rounds or rapid question sessions to spark new ideas. • Provide post-workshop materials (links, summaries, presentation resources). • Continue fostering broad participation across researchers, emergency planners, educators, and policymakers.

Based on what you’ve learned about CRESCENT, what products/research do you anticipate using? (e.g., CFM viewer and/ or CVM viewer). Is there a working group or special interest group that you would like to engage with?

Participants are most eager to engage with interactive, map-based data products (CFM, CVM, dashboards, and catalogues) and scenario-building tools that have direct applications for emergency management and public communication. Specific interests are highlighted in the table below:

Table A6: Summary of main products of interest and use cases from evaluation responses

Research product/resource	Specific use/interest
Community models and viewers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CFM (Community Fault Model) – valued for planning, scenario creation, and hazard visualization. • CVM (Community Velocity Model) – of interest for improving modeling accuracy and applications such as ShakeAlert.
Data hubs, dashboards, and catalogs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enthusiasm for a Cascadia ‘data dashboard’ and related GIS-based data hubs, catalogues, and viewers (e.g., the CPAL viewer). • Interest in state geologic catalogs (Oregon and Washington) and integrating these with CRESCENT tools.
Scenario and risk tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desire for a scenario repository featuring pre-built tabletop exercise scenarios, including sector-specific ones (e.g., for schools). • Particular interest in ground failure and liquefaction maps, Critical Energy Hub risk tools, and ground motion modeling outputs.
Communication, outreach, and education products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requests for resources supporting public engagement, science communication, and workforce development. • Interest in seed grants that foster collaboration and outreach.

Do you have suggestions for how CRESCENT can better foster bidirectional communication between CRESCENT scientists and the wider earthquake research/resilience community?

Participants emphasized the importance of continuing and expanding CRESCENT’s workshops and meetings as key venues for two-way communication and collaboration. They encouraged greater inclusion of diverse partners, such as local policymakers, smaller and tribal communities, and non-scientific stakeholders, alongside scientists and technical professionals. Suggestions included creating action committees, “ask an expert” forums, and online or newsletter-based communities to maintain dialogue between meetings. Respondents also highlighted the value of clear, accessible communication

tools to broaden understanding and engagement, including visual aids, recorded webinars, and audience-tailored website features. Several noted that while CRESCENT is already using many channels effectively, there is room to strengthen bidirectional flow, integrating with other organizations and existing efforts, and “meeting communities where they are.”

We are planning to publish the Cascadia connections map (from the introductory session, day 1). How might you use this resource in your work? Do you have ideas for how CRESCENT can better foster interorganizational collaboration?

Table A7: Summary of Cascadia connections map uses/recommendations from evaluation responses

Potential use of Cascadia Connections map	Recommendations
Directory of organizations for practical networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a public, interactive, digital version allowing users to click on organizations for brief descriptions, key contacts, and website links. • Include contact lists or directories (names, emails, roles, and areas of expertise) to support direct collaboration and communication.
Strategic coordination and research alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the map to connect subgroups and projects—e.g., periodic updates, newsletters, or forums that highlight new partnerships or shared initiatives. • Perform gap analyses and identify interdependencies among organizations. • Facilitate introductions among members - position CRESCENT as a networking intermediary that connects individuals across agencies and disciplines. • Support research-to-practice translation by helping users identify where to share or validate scientific data and products with end users. • Link to or align with existing efforts such as the <i>ShakeAlert EPIcenter Partnership</i> and <i>ShakeOut</i>, leveraging their established outreach and collaboration models. • Support ongoing, in-person convenings and co-developed forums for cross-sector interaction. • Encourage continued feedback and iteration to refine how the tool best supports collaboration and decision-making.
Education, training, and public engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt the activity format for professional development, school-community partnerships, and volunteer or community preparedness trainings. • Use the visualization to communicate the complexity of Cascadia resilience efforts to the public, elected officials, and interest groups—emphasizing hope and solutions. • Incorporate the map into orientation and onboarding for new or existing staff to build awareness of the broader Cascadia network.

Appendix 5 – Cascadia Connections Map

Copyright © 2025 Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center / InfoGraphics Lab, University of Oregon